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Vasyl Orlyk, Mark Pyzyk

A hoard of Pontic coins from the time of Mithridates VI Eupator from the chora of Olbia

Key words: Olbia, coins, Hoard, Mithridates VI Eupator, Pontus.

Cuvinte cheie: Olbia, monede, deposit, Mithridates VI Eupator, Marea Neagră.

Ключевые слова: Ольбья, монеты, клад, Митридат VI Евпатор, Черное Море.

Vasyl Orlyk, Mark Pyzyk

A hoard of Pontic coins from the time of Mithridates VI Eupator from the chora of Olbia

A hoard of bronze coins, consisting of Pontic and Paphlagonian coins from the reign of Mithradates VI Eupator, was found in 2022 in the Ochakiv district of the Mykolaiv oblast of Ukraine. This hoard is an important source for the history of monetary circulation in the northern Black Sea region as a whole, as well as for Olbia and its economic network in the northwestern Black Sea coastal and inland regions, in particular. Pontic coins in the hoard, minted by Mithradates VI, represent two successive groups (Groups 3 and 4) of bronze coins of the heavy Denomination A and the middle-weight Denomination B, minted in Amisus (80%), Amastris (10%), and Sinope (10%). Comparison with finds—both in single finds and hoards—discovered in the northern Black Sea region containing bronze coins minted in the Pontic kingdom of Mithradates VI, confirms the position of Karyshkovskii, formulated more than half a century earlier, that Olbia was by far the most well-represented city for finds of Pontic bronze coins of Groups 3 and 4. Hoards found on the territory of Pontus are characterized by a significant portion of coins from Amisus (72.12%), which may suggest that relations were stronger between Olbia and Pontus than Pontus and Paphlagonia. Our results support the conclusions of Saprykin, that the coinage of Amisus was dominant in Olbia. The bulk of the hoard (97.06%) is made up of coins of the middle-weight Denomination B, among which the Ares-Sword type comprises 32.07% and the Aegis-Nike type 67.83%. The hoard discussed in this article indicates that demand on the Olbian market for small change at the end of the 2nd century BCE and the first two decades of the 1st drove the import of significant quantities of the bronze coinage of Mithridates VI, primarily of the medium-weight Denomination B. For this reason, in this period, coins of smaller denominations were minted (albeit in limited numbers) in Olbia itself.

Vasyl Orlyk, Mark Pyzyk

Un tezaur de monede pontice din timpul lui Mithridates VI Eupator din chora de la Olbia

Un tezaur de monede de bronz, format din monede pontice și paphlagoniene din timpul domniei lui Mithradates VI Eupator, a fost descoperit în 2022 în districtul Ochakiv din regiunea Mykolaiv din Ucraina. Acest tezaur este o sursă importantă pentru istoria circulației monetare în regiunea nordică a Mării Negre în ansamblu, precum și pentru Olbia și rețeaua sa economică din regiunile de coastă și interioare din nord-vestul Mării Negre, în special. Monedele pontice din tezaur, bătute de Mithradates al VI-lea, reprezintă două grupe succesive (grupele 3 și 4) de monede de bronz de valoare grea A și de valoare medie B, bătute în Amisus (80%), Amastris (10%) și Sinope (10%). Compararea cu descoperirile - atât în descoperiri izolate, cât și în tezaure - descoperite în nordul regiunii Mării Negre, care conțin monede de bronz bătute în regatul pontic al lui Mithradates VI, confirmă poziția lui Karyshkovskii, formulată cu mai bine de jumătate de secol mai devreme, conform căreia Olbia a fost de departe orașul cel mai bine reprezentat în ceea ce privește descoperirile de monede pontice de bronz din grupele 3 și 4. Tezaurul descoperit pe teritoriul Pontului sunt caracterizate de o parte semnificativă de monede din Amisus (72,12%), ceea ce poate sugera că relațiile dintre Olbia și Pont erau mai puternice decât între Pont și Paphlagonia. Rezultatele noastre susțin concluziile lui Saprykin, conform cărora monedele din Amisus erau dominante în Olbia. Cea mai mare parte a tezaurului (97,06%) este alcătuită din monede de greutate medie de denomiția B, printre care tipul Ares-Sword cuprinde 32,07% și tipul Aegis-Nike 67,83%. Tezaurul analizat în acest articol indică faptul că cererea de mărunțișuri de pe piața olbiană la sfârșitul secolului al II-lea î.Chr. și în primele două decenii ale secolului I a determinat importul unor cantități semnificative de monede de bronz ale lui Mithridates al VI-lea, în principal de tipul de greutate medie B. Din acest motiv, în această perioadă, monede de valoare mai mică au fost bătute (deși în număr limitat) chiar în Olbia.

Васил Орлик, Марк Пызык

Клад понтийских монет времен Митридата VI Евпатора из хоры Ольвии

В 2022 г. в Очаковском районе Николаевской области Украины был найден клад бронзовых монет, состоящий из понтийских и пафлагонских монет эпохи правления Митрадата VI Евпатора. Этот клад является важным источником по истории денежного обращения Северного Причерноморья в целом, а также Ольвии и ее экономической сети в северо-западном Причерноморье и внутренних регионах, в частности. Понтийские монеты в кладе, чеканенные Митрадатов VI, представляют собой две последовательные группы (группы 3 и 4) бронзовых монет тяжелого номинала А и среднего но-

минала В, чеканенных в Амисусе (80%), Амастрисе (10%) и Синопе (10%). Сравнение с находками - как единичными, так и кладами, обнаруженными в Северном Причерноморье, содержащими бронзовые монеты, отчеканенные в Понтийском царстве Митридата VI, подтверждает сформулированное более чем за полвека до этого положение Карышковского о том, что Ольвия была наиболее представленным городом по находкам понтийских бронзовых монет 3-й и 4-й групп. Для кладов, найденных на территории Понта, характерна значительная доля монет из Амисуса (72,12%), что может свидетельствовать о более тесных связях между Ольвией и Понтом, чем Понтом и Пафлагонией. Наши результаты подтверждают выводы Сапрыкина о том, что в Ольвии преобладала чеканка монет Амисуса. Основную часть клада (97,06%) составляют монеты среднего веса номинала В, среди которых тип Арес-Меч составляет 32,07%, а тип Эгида-Ника - 67,83%. Рассматриваемый в данной статье клад свидетельствует о том, что спрос на мелкую мелочь на ольвийском рынке в конце II в. до н.э. и в первые два десятилетия I в. обусловил импорт значительного количества бронзовых монет Митридата VI, прежде всего среднего веса номинала В. По этой причине в этот период в самой Ольвии чеканились (хотя и в ограниченном количестве) монеты более мелких номиналов.

Introduction

At the end of the 2nd century BCE and the start of the 1st, the Greek cities of the northern Black Sea region “appear to have been united into a single political unit, becoming a part of the Pontic kingdom of Mithradates Eupator” [Shelov 1983, 40]. The first to come under the authority of the Pontic king were Chersonesus and Olbia. The most convincing modern chronology of this process has been put forward by Vinogradov (1989, 259) and Saprykin (1996, 135-137), who propose that it occurred before 109 BCE. The simultaneous accession of Olbia and Chersonesus into the Pontic kingdom at the beginning of the final decade of the 2nd century is supported both by numismatic discoveries in the Greek cities of the northern Black Sea, as well as by separate finds of bronze coins from Pontus and Paphlagonia. These suggest that “the near simultaneity in appearance of autonomous bronze coins in Olbia and Chersonesus around 111-105 is the result of the near simultaneous entry of both cities into the Pontic state after the successful campaigns of Diophantus of Scythia” [Saprykin 1996, 137]. By the end of the 2nd century BCE, the power of Mithridates VI had extended as far as the Bosporus [Molev 1974, 72]. Bronze coins of Pontus and Paphlagonia became important on regional currency markets, receiving “their own exchange rates” [Maksimova 1956, 228]. Golenko sensibly notes that, if in the 2nd century BCE, on these territories, “the widest reaching was the small bronze coin, the denomination which Shelov calls a ‘chalkous’, while quadrachalkoi and dichalkoi are known in only a single type, then under Mithridates the situation changed dramatically... with obols and tetracha-

lkoi becoming the leading denominations, having been unknown, with one exception, earlier on the Bosporus” [Golenko 1964, 65]. In contemporary numismatics, the bronze coinage of the Pontic and Paphlagonian cities in the time of Mithradates VI can be divided into five groupings (or denominations) according to weight and diameter: AA (c. 16-21 gr.), A (c. 11-14 gr.), B (c. 5-8 gr.), C (c. 3-4.5 gr.), and D (c. 1.5-2.5 gr.), which following Imhoof-Blumer are traditionally labeled obols (AA, A), tetrachalkoi (B), dichalkoi (C), and chalkoi (D) [Orlyk & Mekh 2022, 11].

The influence of the Mithridatic kingdom expanded not only across the northern Black Sea region, but all along its borderlands, where northern Black Sea Greeks had traditionally maintained economic ties. Thus Olbia, in particular, became an emporion for Pontus in the northern Black Sea area. After all, the middle Dnieper region had traditionally fallen into the trade sphere of Olbia [Boltrik 2000], along which it is likely that livestock, meat, as well as “expensive pelts-from beavers and other animals” were exported from the forest-grasslands of the Dnieper’s right bank [Maksimov 1972, 75]. Access to these goods could be procured through either purchase or through barter. And it was through Olbia that coins of the Mithridatic state, as well as those of other ancient Greeks, made their way into the forest and forest-grassland zones of Ukraine [Mielczarek 1989; Skoryi, Zimovets 2014; Mielczarek, Orlyk 2019; Nikolaev 2020; Orlyk, Kotsur, Tsyganenko 2019, Orlyk, Orlyk 2020; Nikolaev 2021; Orlyk 2021; Nikolaev, Tsyganenko 2022; Orlyk 2022; Orlyk, Mekh 2022; Orlyk, Kolesnichenko 2022]. The existence of monetary and commodity exchange in

these regions between local barbarian populations and Greeks is supported not only by the presence of significant numbers of coin finds, but also by monetary assemblages and concentrations of coin finds within narrow areas.

The historical problem of monetary circulation and Olbian coinage in the time of Mithridates VI has been reflected in the work of several generations of scholars, and in particular in that of Zograf (1940), Golenko (1964), Maksimova (1956), Karishkovskii (1965, 1988, 2003), Shelov (1983), Saprykin (1996, 2007), Krapivina (2005), Nikolaev (2013, 2016, 2019, 2020), Orlyk (2021, 2022), as well as others.

Recent decades have seen the expansion in the use of metal detectors in Ukraine, as in most other countries in the world. As a result, in nearly every country, often in spite of explicit, strict legal prohibitions, the provenance of single coin finds and hoards goes unreported [Pyzyk 2021], with finds themselves—rather than ending up in a museum—being dispersed and therefore lost to scholarly research. Ukraine is sadly no exception. Ukrainian archaeologists Skoryi and Zimovets emphasize that in the last decade the number of ancient coins finds in the forest-grassland zone has grown, and nearly all of them, including those from the hill-forts of the Scythian period, “were unfortunately discovered outside the course of archaeological activity” [Skoryi, Zimovets 2014, 143] – meaning through the use of metal detectors. Contemporary realities are forcing numismatists to significantly expand their base of scholarly research, especially in tracking new numismatic finds, among which are materials found on treasure-hunting forums and in private correspondence with metal detectorists [Kotsur 2017]. The use of such “new”, unconventional sources of information (at least from the perspective of 20th century scholars) has been successful, and successfully tested, by 21st century archaeologists [Myzgin 2015], especially by Polish scholars [Dymowski 2011, 2016] through the mapping of coin find sites with clear, or relatively clear, provenance. Among several similar coin finds found on the internet are coins from the Ochakiv district of the Mikolaev oblast – that is, from the former territory of Olbia. Analysis of these finds allows us to expand our understanding of the economic history of Olbia and its people in the 2nd and 1st centuries BCE, as well as to dispel some entrenched myths.

Near the end of 2022, sixty-eight bronze coins of the Pontic kingdom of Mithradates VI were put up for sale on the numismatic auction site, Violity, by a resident of the oblast of Mykolaiv. Visual inspection of their images, and specifically the patina and corrosion on the surface of some, gave us reason to believe that these coins might belong to one find, or at most two. We received confirmation of this from the owner. The coins really do belong to the coin hoard found in 2022 in the Ochakiv district of the Mykolaiv oblast. According to information that the authors received in the course of their correspondence, the hoard was discovered at a depth of 90-110 cm. It was likely stored in an organic container (perhaps leather or fabric) which decomposed through interaction with the soil.

The portion of the coins that made up a sort of carapace (an outer layer of coins) for the hoard was heavily corroded, but the coins nestled within were well preserved. In studying coins from the Ochakiv district it is necessary to account for the fact that the waters at the bottom of the “Dnieper-Bug estuary are highly alkaline, meaning a pH within the range of 7.4-8.7” [Kutishchev et al., 327], and that in turn, coastal soils are likewise highly alkaline, which has negative effects on metallic objects found therein, including bronze coins.

The authors managed to procure photographs of the sixty-eight coins in this monetary assemblage, as well as to directly handle five coins from the hoard. Let us now turn to a more detailed analysis of the assemblage.

Hoard Catalogue

A detailed study of the aforementioned monetary assemblage allows us to put together a catalogue (Table 1) and to organize its fifty-five coins according to their type and date of production, as well as assign mints to thirty of them. Unfortunately, we could not identify the type of thirteen coins of the middle-weight Denomination B on account of their unsatisfactory state of preservation.

Table 1. Catalogue of a hoard of bronze coins of the Pontic kingdom of Mithridates VI Eupator, found in the Ochakiv district of Mykolaiv oblast in 2022.

No.	Description	Catalogue	Chronology and place of coinage	Wt (g) / Diam. (mm)
1	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Athena right, wearing crested helmet. <i>Rev.</i> Perseus standing facing, holding head of Medusa and harpa; decapitated body of Medusa below; AMI-ΣΟΥ; monogram below inscription l. ΜΕ, below r. Ξ Fig. 1,1	SNG BM Black Sea #1173	105-90 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 29
2	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Athena right, wearing crested helmet. <i>Rev.</i> Perseus standing facing, holding head of Medusa and harpa; decapitated body of Medusa below; Fig. 1,2		105-90 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 33
4	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Ares in Attic helmet right. <i>Rev.</i> Sword in sheath AMI-ΣΟΥ, above l. ☼; above r. IB, below l. Α, below r. ? Fig. 1,3	SNG BM Black Sea #1159	105-90 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 95-90 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 21
5	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Ares in Attic helmet right. <i>Rev.</i> Sword in sheath AMI-ΣΟΥ, above l. ☼; above r. IB, below l. ΒΚ Fig. 1,4	SNG BM Black Sea #1161	105-90 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 95-90 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 19
6	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Ares in Attic helmet right. <i>Rev.</i> Sword in sheath AMI-ΣΟΥ, above l. ☼; above r. IB, below l. ΒΚ Fig. 1,5	SNG BM Black Sea #1161	105-90 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 95-90 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	8,37 20
7	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Ares in Attic helmet right. <i>Rev.</i> Sword in sheath AMI-ΣΟΥ above l. ☼, above r. ΑΡ, below l. ΒΚ, below r. possibly ΑΚ or ΑΡ Fig. 1,6	SNG BM Black Sea #1162	111-105 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 95-90 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	8.28 20
9	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Ares in Attic helmet right. <i>Rev.</i> Sword in sheath AMI-ΣΟΥ above ll. ☼, above r. ΑΡ, below l. ΒΚ, below r. ΑΚ Fig. 1,7	SNG BM Black Sea #1162	111-105 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 95-90 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 18×19
10	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Ares in Attic helmet right. <i>Rev.</i> Sword in sheath AMI-ΣΟΥ, above l. ☼; above r. IB, below l. ΒΚ, below r. ? Fig. 1,8	SNG BM Black Sea -	111-105 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 95-90 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 18

11	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Ares in Attic helmet right. <i>Rev.</i> Sword in sheath AMI-ΣΟΥ, below l. Fig. 1,9	SNG Stancomb 677	105-90 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 95-90 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	9.02 19,5×20,5
12	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Ares in Attic helmet right. <i>Rev.</i> Sword in sheath AMI-ΣΟΥ, above l. ; below l. ?, below r.?	SNG BM Black Sea ##1147- 1165	105-90 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 95-90 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 20 MM
	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Ares in Attic helmet right. <i>Rev.</i> Sword in sheath AMI-ΣΟΥ, above l. ; below l. ?, below r.?	SNG BM Black Sea ##1147- 1165	105-90 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 95-90 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 20 MM
13	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Ares in Attic helmet right. <i>Rev.</i> Sword in sheath <AMI>-ΣΟ<Υ>. Fig. 1,10	SNG BM Black Sea ##1147- 1165	105-90 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 95-90 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 20 MM
14	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Ares in Attic helmet right. <i>Rev.</i> Sword in sheath ΣΙΝΩ-ΠΗΣ Fig. 1,11	SNG BM Black Sea ##1528- 1530	111-105 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 95-90 BC (Callataÿ) Sinope	- 21
15	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Ares in Attic helmet right. <i>Rev.</i> Sword in sheath <ΣΙΝΩ>-ΠΗ<Σ>	SNG BM Black Sea ##1528- 1530	111-105 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 95-90 BC (Callataÿ) Sinope	- 20
16	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Ares in Attic helmet right. <i>Rev.</i> Sword in sheath		111-105 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 95-90 BC (Callataÿ)	- 19,5
17	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Ares in Attic helmet right. <i>Rev.</i> Sword in sheath		111-105 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 95-90 BC (Callataÿ)	- 18
18	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Ares in Attic helmet right. <i>Rev.</i> Sword in sheath		111-105 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 95-90 BC (Callataÿ)	- 20
19	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Ares in Attic helmet right. <i>Rev.</i> Sword in sheath		111-105 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 95-90 BC (Callataÿ)	- 22
21	<i>Obv.</i> Head of Ares in Attic helmet right. <i>Rev.</i> Sword in sheath (25R)		111-105 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 95-90 BC (Callataÿ)	- 22
20	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right AMI-ΣΟΥ, below l. , below r.? Fig. 1,12	SNG BM Black Sea #1177	105-90 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 19×21
22	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right AMI-ΣΟΥ, below l. Fig. 1,13 31R	SNG BM Black Sea #1188	105-90 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 21

23	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right AMI-ΣΟΥ, below l. $\overline{\text{M}}\overline{\text{E}}$, below r. $\overline{\text{X}}\overline{\text{I}}$ Fig. 1,14	SNG BM Black Sea #1190	105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 21
24	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right AMI-ΣΟΥ, below l. $\overline{\text{M}}\overline{\text{E}}$, below r. $\overline{\text{X}}\overline{\text{I}}$ Fig. 1,15	SNG BM Black Sea #1190	105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	6,25 22
25	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right <AMI>-ΣΟΥ below r. ? Fig. 1,16	SNG BM Black Sea ##1177- 1191	105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 21×22
26	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right AMI-<ΣΟΥ> Fig. 1,17	SNG BM Black Sea ##1177- 1191	105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 22,5
27	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right AMI-<ΣΟΥ> Fig. 1,18	SNG BM Black Sea ##1177- 1191	105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 21
28	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right <AMI>-ΣΟ<Υ> Fig. 1,19	SNG BM Black Sea ##1177- 1191	105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 21
29	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right AMI-<ΣΟΥ>, below l. $\overline{\text{M}}\overline{\text{E}}$, Fig. 1,20	SNG BM Black Sea ##1177- 1191	105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 20
30	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right AMI-<ΣΟΥ>	SNG BM Black Sea ##1177- 1191	105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 23
31	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right <AM>I-ΣΟ<Υ>	SNG BM Black Sea ##1177- 1191	105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 23
32	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right <A>MI-ΣΟ<Υ>	SNG BM Black Sea ##1177- 1191	105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ) Amisus	- 22
33	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right ΑΜΑΣ-ΤΡΕΩΣ Fig. 1,21	SNG BM Black Sea ##1315- 1318	105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ) Amastris	- 20×24
34	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right <A>ΜΑΣ-ΤΡΕ<ΩΣ> Fig. 1,22	SNG BM Black Sea ##1315- 1318	105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ) Amastris	- 22

35	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right ΑΜΑΣ-ΤΡΕΩΣ Fig. 1,23	SNG BM Black Sea ##1315- 1318	105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ) Amastris	- 23
36	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right <Σ>ΙΝ-ΩΠΗΣ Fig. 1,24	SNG BM Black Sea ##1536- 1540	105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ) Sinope	7,15 20×18,4
37	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 21
38	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 22×23
39	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 21
40	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 21
41	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 21
42	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 25
43	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 23
44	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 21×23
45	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 23×21
46	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 23×21,5
47	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 21
48	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 20
49	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof- Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 20

50	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 21
51	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 21
52	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 23
53	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 22
54	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 21
55	<i>Obv.</i> Aegis with gorgoneion <i>Rev.</i> Nike advancing right		105-90 BC (Imhoof-Blumer) 90-85 BC (Callataÿ)	- 23

All of the coins from this hoard belong to one of two previously mentioned groups (Groups 3 and 4) of the bronze heavy Denomination A and middle-weight Denomination B, minted in the cities of Amisus, Amastris, and Sinope. Regarding the chronology of production of these types, among numismatists, there are two main schemata for the bronze coins of the Pontic kingdom of Mithradates VI, specifically Imhoof-Blumer's and de Callataÿ's. According to the schema of Imhoof-Blumer, the coins of the middle-weight Denomination B of the Ares-Sword type were minted between 111-105 BCE (i.e., Group 3), while the coins of the heavy Denomination A of the Athena-Perseus type, as well as coins of the middle-weight Denomination B, of both the Ares-Sword type with the letters IB and the coins of the Aegis-Nike type, were minted between 105-90 BCE (Group 4). According to de Callataÿ, all coins of the Ares-Sword type were minted between 95-90 BCE (Group 3), and the coins of the heavy Denomination A of the Athena-Perseus type and the middle-weight Denomination B of the Aegis-Nike type were minted between 90-85 BCE (Group 4). Stolba, however, provides good arguments on the basis of the excavation of Scythian Naples, where coins of the middle-weight Denomination B of the Ares-Sword type, minted in Amisus, were "uncovered in the total destruction layer of the Southern Palace (Layer D1)" [Stolba 2005, 30], which was most likely destroyed in 108 BCE, "seemingly, dur-

ing the second campaign of Diophantus against the Scythians" [Stolba 2005, 30]. For this reason, emissions of the middle-weight Denomination B of the Ares-Sword type should still be attributed to the earlier period – that is, their production began before 108 BCE, as Imhoof-Blumer suggested.

Following this, if the coins of the middle-weight Denomination B of the Ares-Sword type were minted in the last decade of the 2nd century BCE, then the next group of coins after it to which both the middle-weight Denomination B Ares-Sword type with letters IB and the Aegis-Nike type belong ought to have been minted at the start of the 1st century BCE. Thus, their production might have begun around 100 BCE. In determining the chronology of coins of these types, it is necessary to keep in mind that they are the most common bronze coins of the Pontic kingdom of Mithradates VI, and that Aegis-Nike type coins known to modern scholars significantly outnumber those of the Ares-Sword type, which may indicate a far longer period of minting for the former than the latter. For this reason, it may be hypothesized that coins of the middle-weight Denomination B of the Ares-Sword type were minted around 110-100 BCE, and those of the Aegis-Nike type around 100-85 BCE. In the northern Black Sea region, Olbia outperforms all other cities in finds of Pontic bronze coins of Groups 3 and 4 [Karyshkovskii 1965, 65-66; Saprykin 1996, 169], and for this reason the discovery in 2022 of the hoards discussed

Fig. 1

here, found on Olbian territory and containing coins from these groups alone, seems natural.

Only two coins in the 2022 Ochakiv hoard are of the heavy Denomination A Athena-Perseus type. All sixty-five others are of the middle-weight Denomination B. Categorizing the hoard according to type and mint, and taking into account their condition, of fifty-three coins, the middle-weight Denomination B Ares-Sword type comprises 32.07%, while the Aegis-Nike type comprises 67.93%. Regarding mint, which could only be identified for thirty coins, 80% are from Amisus, 10% from Amastris, and 10% from Sinope. These are not representative, however, because 55.88% of coins could not be given a mint attribution on account of poor preservation. Nevertheless, it is unlikely that the majority of those coins came from other mints in the Pontic kingdom. Thus, it is more likely that these coins came to the northern Black Sea region, and specifically to Olbia, from Amisus or from one of its trading partners in the Pontus. Data on hoards found in the Pontus, in which “Amisean bronze coins exceed those from such centres as Sinope, Amastris, Gazioura, Komana, Chabakta and others more than seven times (72.12% against 12% for coins from Sinope, which are the second most frequent class of coins)” [Saprykin 2007, 200], supports our conclusion regarding the Pontic origins of the coins from our hoard. The 2022 Ochakiv hoard re-affirms Saprykin’s conclusion that “in Olbia and Chersonesos Amisean coins are dominant” [Saprykin 2007, 200].

The composition of coin types in our hoard indicates that these coins entered the territory of Olbia and were buried in the period when the heavy Denomination A Athena-Perseus type and the middle-weight Denomination B Aegis-Nike type were minted, at a time when they circulated in parallel with the Ares-Sword type that is, in the second decade of the 1st century BCE.

Discussion: The role of the bronze coinage of the Pontic kingdom of Mithridates VI in the monetary circulation of the northwestern Black Sea region

After the unification of the northern and southern Black Sea regions under the kingship of Mithridates VI, trade between the various regions in the new state resumed, and as a result

the number of Mithridatic coins circulating in the Greek cities of the northern Black Sea, at the time suffering a significant shortage of their own coinage, increased. Karyshkovskii rightly notes that “before Olbia fell under Mithridates’ rule, the city likely experienced significant demand for exchange bronze: such a need existed under Skilurus, as evidenced by the countermarking on earlier coins during his reign” [Karyshkovskii 1965, 67]. Demand in urban markets for small change at the end of the 2nd century and first decade of the 1st century BCE attracted significant volumes of bronze coinage minted in Pontus under Mithridates, usually of the middle-weight Denomination B, and because of this Olbia itself minted coins of even smaller denomination in the same period. Shelov, analyzing the coinage of Olbia in the time of Mithridates VI, notes that only a few types of small bronze coins can be dated to the period of his reign, most probably a *dichalkous* (weighing c. 4.5 gr.) featuring a helmeted Athena and weapons (a shield and spear), as well as a *chalkous* (c. 2.3 gr.) featuring Apollo (or a kithara) and a Dolphin between a Dioscuric cap and tripod [Shelov 1983, 51]. Shelov draws attention to the textural and stylistic similarities of the two types, which may indicate that they were issued simultaneously or within a short time of one another. Nevertheless, Olbian coin production was insignificant while the city was under the rule of Mithridates VI, and specimens of these coins are quite rare on contemporary coin markets. The bronze coinage of the Pontic kingdom of Mithridates, specifically the middle-weight Denomination B, formed the basis for small change circulation in Olbia and its related territories in the northwestern Black Sea region.

Conclusions

1. The hoard found in the Ochakiv district of the Mykolaiv oblast in 2022 was a coin purse or wallet containing coins that were representative of the basic elements of small change circulation in Olbia and its attendant territories at the end of the 2nd century and first decade of the 1st century BCE.

2. All coins of the heavy Denomination A and the middle-weight Denomination B of the Pontic kingdom of Mithridates VI from this hoard can be divided into two consecutive groups (Groups 3 and 4) of bronze coins minted in the cities of

Amisus, Amastris, and Sinope, at a time when all three circulated simultaneously which is to say the second decade of the 1st century BCE.

3. An analysis of hoard composition supports the theory that Olbia was the most common place that Pontic bronze coins of Groups 3 and 4 were to be found.

4. Coins from Amisus comprise 80%, Amastris 10%, and Sinope 10% of the identified coins in the hoard, which supports the conclu-

sions of previous studies of monetary circulation in Olbia in the time of Mithridates VI, according to which Amisus dominated the Olbian currency market.

5. The most common bronze coinage in Olbia and in the northern Black Sea region, among the bronze coins of the Pontic kingdom under Mithridates VI, was the middle-weight Denomination B. In our study of this hoard, these middle-weight coins comprise 97.06 % of the total.

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